

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

FINANCING OF THE SUSTAINABLE TOURISM INDUSTRY IN GEORGIA

Tamar Gamsakhurdia

Doctor of Economic Sciences, *Professor, School of Business and Management
Grigol Robakidze University, Georgia*

Slava Fetelava

Doctor of Economics (PhD), Associate Professor
*School of Business and Management
Grigol Robakidze University, Georgia*

Abstract

Tourism plays a vital role in generating revenue for Georgia. The influx of tourists contributes to various sectors of the economy, including accommodation, transportation, food and beverage services, entertainment, and retail. Furthermore, tourism can have a multiplier effect on the economy. When tourists spend money in Georgia, it circulates through the economy, generating income for various businesses and individuals. This increased economic activity leads to further job creation, stimulates investment, and contributes to the overall development of the country. Additionally, tourism also generates indirect revenue through associated sectors such as agriculture, construction, and manufacturing, which cater to the needs of tourists and the tourism industry. In the process of the research are used general scientific methods (systemic, structural, functional) and private methods (graphic and those of conformity). Official statistical data existing in the country as well as the data and evaluations officially published by international organizations are also used.

Based on the research done we would like to provide several recommendations aiming to provide a foundation for improving the financing of sustainable tourism in Georgia, enabling the region to develop and support tourism initiatives that are economically viable, socially inclusive, and environmentally responsible.

Keywords: Financing, Tourism, Financial innovations, Expenses, International organization, Sustainable tourism.

Introduction

Tourism has a significant impact on the economy of Georgia, particularly in terms of generating revenue and employment opportunities. Over a million (1,094,400) foreign visitors visited Georgia in the second quarter of 2022. This is almost 200% more than in the same period last year. However, it still lags behind pre-pandemic levels, when Georgia received twice as many foreign visitors in 2019, at 2.2 million. Tourist spending in the second quarter of 2022 amounted to 2.3 billion GEL (about 850 million dollars) Tourism also has a significant impact on employment in Georgia. According to the Georgian National Tourism Administration, the tourism sector employed over 100,000 people in 2019, which is approximately 6% of the country's total workforce. In addition to the direct economic impact, tourism also has indirect benefits for Georgia's economy, including increased demand for goods and services such as food, transportation, and accommodations. This can stimulate growth in related sectors, such as agriculture and construction, leading to further economic benefits.

Based on the research done we would like to provide several recommendations aiming to provide a foundation for improving the financing of sustainable tourism in Georgia, enabling the region to develop and support tourism initiatives that are economically viable, socially inclusive, and environmentally responsible.

Methodology

The purpose of the research is to identify the basic challenges of financing sustainable tourism develop-

ment in Georgia and express a vision regarding the industry's prospects. This can be accomplished through various research activities, including:

1. Identifying financing challenges: The research aims to identify and analyze the key challenges that hinder the financing of sustainable tourism development in Georgia. This includes factors such as limited access to capital, inadequate financial mechanisms, lack of investor awareness, or the absence of dedicated funding sources for sustainable tourism projects.

2. Assessing current financing practices: The research seeks to evaluate the existing financing practices in the Georgian tourism industry, including the sources of funding, investment patterns, and the effectiveness of financial mechanisms. This assessment can help identify gaps, inefficiencies, and areas that require improvement.

3. Examining policy and regulatory frameworks: This includes analyzing government policies, legislation, and regulations related to tourism and sustainable development, as well as the presence of incentives or support programs for sustainable tourism initiatives.

4. Conducting stakeholder analysis: The research involves engaging with various stakeholders, such as government agencies, tourism industry professionals, financial institutions, investors, and sustainability experts. By studying the surveys, the research aims to gather perspectives, experiences, and insights from these stakeholders to better understand the challenges and opportunities in financing sustainable tourism development.

5. Proposing recommendations and a vision: Based on the findings, the research aims to provide recommendations and propose a vision for the future of sustainable tourism financing in Georgia. This may involve suggesting innovative financing models to address the identified challenges and enhance the prospects of the industry.

The ultimate goal of the research is to contribute to the knowledge base surrounding sustainable tourism financing in Georgia and offer insights that can inform stakeholders in developing strategies and actions to overcome financing challenges and foster the sustainable growth of the tourism industry.

Tourism Development Financing directions Top of Form Top of Form

Tourism has a significant impact on the economy of Georgia, particularly in terms of generating revenue and employment opportunities. Over a million (1,094,400) foreign visitors visited Georgia in the second quarter of 2022. This is almost 200% more than in the same period last year. However, it still lags behind pre-pandemic levels, when Georgia received twice as many foreign visitors in 2019, at 2.2 million. Tourist spending in the second quarter of 2022 amounted to 2.3 billion GEL (about 850 million dollars). Tourism also has a significant impact on employment and stability of national currency in Georgia (Dilanchiev, Taktakishvili, 2021). According to the Georgian National Tourism Administration, the tourism sector employed over 100,000 people in 2019, which is approximately 6% of the country's total workforce) (Geostat.ge 2022).

According to a report by the World Economy and Tourism Council (WTTC), 483,000 jobs were created in Georgia's tourism sector before the covid 19 pandemic event, also known as a Cononomic Crisis (Papava, Charaia, 2020; Charaia, Lashkhi, 2020). Georgia ranked 78th in the world in terms of the share of direct employment in tourism and travel. In 2018, the share of employees in the tourism and related industries was 7.8%. Georgia ranked 29th among 145 countries of the world (WTTC . 2021).

In addition to the direct economic impact, tourism also has indirect benefits for Georgia's economy, including increased demand for goods and services such as food, transportation, and accommodations. This can stimulate growth in related sectors, such as agriculture and construction, leading to further economic benefits (Meladze et al., 2022).

Based on all the mentioned, it is clear that financing sustainable tourism development in Georgia is important because it can help to promote economic growth, create jobs, and generate income for local communities, while also preserving the country's rich cultural heritage (Kadagidze, Piranashvili, 2018). a great support in this process can be fintech technologies, especially to ease the support for smaller businesses

(Lashkhi et al, 2022). By investing in sustainable tourism initiatives, we can help to ensure that the benefits of tourism are shared more equitably, and that the negative impacts of tourism are minimized.

For the development of sustainable tourism, the participation of representatives of the state, international or private business in this process is of great importance. There are many different actors who are interested in financing sustainable tourism development in Georgia. These could include:

1. The Georgian government - The government may be interested in financing sustainable cultural tourism development in order to promote economic growth, create jobs, and boost the country's tourism sector.

2. International organizations - International organizations such as the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), the World Bank, and the European Union may be interested in financing sustainable cultural tourism development in Georgia as part of their efforts to promote sustainable development and reduce poverty.

3. Private investors - Private investors may be interested in financing sustainable cultural tourism development in Georgia if they believe that it offers a good return on investment and has the potential to generate significant social and environmental benefits.

4. Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) - NGOs may be interested in financing sustainable cultural tourism development in Georgia as part of their efforts to promote sustainable development, protect cultural heritage, and support local communities.

Over the past decade, the number of tourists in Georgia has been increasing, especially this trend was noticeable in 2009-2013, when their number increased by 300% - from 1.5 million to 5.4 million people. At the same time, total tourism revenue increased from \$475 million to \$1.8 billion over the same period, more than 20 times the global average (GNTA, Georgian tourism in figures, 2015). This circumstance prompted the Ministry of Economy and Sustainable Development of Georgia, the National Tourism Administration to develop "Tourism Development Strategy in Georgia - 2025" (Ministry of Economy and Sustainable Development & GNTA 2015), with the financial and technical support of the World Bank. (The World Bank, 2014). It is known, that for many years the country had a vision, but there was not yet a clear and well-thought-out strategy that could be implemented and monitored (The World Bank, 2015).

Tourism Development Strategy in Georgia included the development of infrastructure, the promotion of the country, the improvement of the quality of service and the diversification of the tourism product. Based on this plan, in 2018, the Government of Georgia developed a marketing, branding and promotion strategy to communicate Georgia brand positioning, visual and verbal identity guidelines, and advertising objectives and target high-growth, high-spending source markets (The World Bank, 2020; Abashidze, 2023).

Table 1.

Distribution of monthly average expenditure spent by inbound visitors of age 15 and older by expenditure categories (Million GEL)

Year	Accommodation	Holiday, leisure, recreation, cultural and sporting activities	Shopping	Local transport	Foods and drinks	Other expenditure	Total expenditure
2015	66.9	56.4	94.2	22.3	81.5	16.8	338.2
2016	85.6	66.7	86.0	26.6	87.6	12.4	365.0
2017	110.6	88.8	101.1	40.3	123.0	16.3	480.1
2018	154.5	119.6	134.3	46.7	188.9	15.7	659.8
2019	168.4	127.4	150.0	53.7	195.3	14.4	709.3
2022	279.3	97.0	139.1	71.6	299.3	14.3	900.7

Source: GEOSTAT, 2022

The table above, which presents the distribution of average monthly expenses incurred during the visits of non-resident guests to Georgia, by category of expenses, in 2015-2022, shows a significant increase in expenses over the period under review.

Georgia's tourism development strategy emphasizes that the country is focused on maximizing the tourism industry's profits (Figures in Tourism, 2016, p.3) and from a financial point of view, it is important to ensure the growth of costs, since an increase in the amount of money spent by foreign visitors in Georgia has a significant impact on the balance of payments (Ernazarov 2018).

Georgia received 3.5 billion US dollars from international tourist visits in 2022, this indicator increased by 182.5 percent compared to 2021, and the income exceeded 107.6 percent compared to 2019. In 2022, 5,426,903 international travelers visited the country – 1885 percent more than in 2021 - while the number of international tourist visits reached 3,652,949 (+131.6% y/y) (GEOSTAT 2022).

Here is some information on the government's budget allocation for tourism development in Georgia over the past five years:

- In 2021, the Georgian government allocated GEL 53.5 million (approximately USD 16.5 million) for the development of the country's tourism sector.
- In 2020, the government allocated GEL 57.4 million (approximately USD 17.8 million) for tourism development.
- In 2019, the government allocated GEL 38.5 million (approximately USD 12 million) for tourism development projects.
- In 2018, the government allocated GEL 49.3 million (approximately USD 15.3 million) for tourism development.

- In 2017, the government allocated GEL 48.3 million (approximately USD 15 million) for tourism development projects (Figures in Tourism 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019).

It's worth noting that these figures represent the total amount allocated for tourism development, which includes not only sustainable cultural tourism development, but also other areas of tourism such as infrastructure development and marketing.

An analysis of the funds spent by the Georgian government in the field of tourism shows that these expenditures are highly variable, depending on different circumstances. The biggest drop in tourism spending came in 2020, when the pandemic all but shut out almost all sectors of the local economy (Charaia et al., 2021; Charaia et al., 2022) and of course foreign tourists and the tourism industry became heavily dependent on domestic travelers and government subsidies. During this period, a large number of subsidies were allocated from the state budget to support the tourism business. In addition, even after the pandemic, the state continues to allocate large amounts of funds. In particular, the amount spent in the budget increased by 99% in 2022, and an increase of another 45% is planned for 2023. It should be noted here that according to the real indicators of the first three quarters of 2022, insufficient funds have been allocated for the development of tourism, which is only 68% of the planned budget (Figure 1. Government Spending on Tourism Support (Million, GEL)).

At the same time, we will see a better picture in terms of spending, if we analyze the share of spending on tourism in GDP, we will see that these figures are increasing, with the only exception being the pandemic (Figure 2. Share of Tourism in GDP and Share of Tourism Spending in the Total Budget).

Figure 1. Government Spending on Tourism Support (Million, GEL)¹

Figure 2. Share of Tourism in GDP and Share of Tourism Spending in the Total Budget²

In addition to government funding, there have been several initiatives aimed at financing sustainable tourism development in Georgia. For example, the European Union has provided funding for a number of tourism-related projects in the country, including initiatives aimed at promoting sustainable tourism and preserving cultural heritage. Similarly, the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) has worked with local communities in Georgia to develop sustainable tourism initiatives that support economic development and cultural preservation.

international organizations such as the World Bank and the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD) and others have provided financing for tourism-related projects in Georgia. For example, the EBRD has provided financing for the development of ski resorts in Georgia, which have the potential to support sustainable tourism development. Here are some notable dates and events related to financing sustainable cultural tourism in Georgia over the past 5 years:

- In 2016, the World Bank provided a \$10 million loan to Georgia to support the development of its tourism sector, including efforts to promote sustainable tourism practices and preserve cultural heritage sites.
- In 2017, the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD) provided a €1.5 million loan to fund the renovation of the historic Rabati Castle in the southern Georgian city of Akhaltsikhe, with the aim of boosting tourism in the region.

- Also in 2018, the EBRD provided a €2 million loan to finance the construction of a new hotel in the town of Kazbegi, in the mountainous northern region of Georgia, with the aim of promoting sustainable tourism in the area.

- In 2019, the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) launched a new project in Georgia called "Improving Rural Development and Livelihoods through Sustainable Tourism," which aims to support the development of sustainable and inclusive tourism in rural areas, with a focus on preserving cultural heritage and promoting local economic growth.

- In 2020, the Georgian government launched a new program called "Spend Your Summer in Georgia," which provides subsidies and tax incentives to local tour operators and hotels to encourage domestic tourism and support the country's tourism industry amid the COVID-19 pandemic.

These are just a few examples, but they give a sense of the ongoing efforts to finance sustainable cultural tourism development in Georgia in recent years.

Finally, private sector investment is also playing an increasingly important role in financing sustainable tourism development in Georgia, particularly in the areas of hospitality and tourism infrastructure development. For example, in 2021, a Turkish hospitality company announced plans to invest USD 100 million in the development of a sustainable tourism complex in Georgia's Black Sea region.

¹ Source: Ministry of Finance (MoF), Georgian National Tourism Administration (GNTA). (2020).

² Source: Ministry of Finance (MoF), Georgian National Tourism Administration (GNTA). (2020).

Financial innovations to finance sustainable tourism development

In order to strengthen the tourism industry and attract more high-yielding tourists to the country, it is of great importance to involve the fintech sector in financing companies involved in the tourism business. Currently, Georgia has been making efforts to leverage fintech in financing tourism (L.Kadagidze, M.Piranashvili, 2021). There are several financial innovations being used in Georgia to finance sustainable tourism development. Here are some examples:

Crowdfunding: Crowdfunding platforms such as Indiegogo (Mamalashvili. 2020) and Kickstarter (Kickstarter. 2023) have been used to fund sustainable tourism projects in Georgia. For example, in 2018, a Georgian company launched a crowdfunding campaign to raise funds for a sustainable tourism project in the Caucasus Mountains.

1. **Impact investing:** Impact investing involves investing in projects or companies that have a positive social or environmental impact. Impact investors may be interested in financing sustainable tourism development in Georgia if they believe that it will have a positive impact on local communities and the environment. Impact investing can provide long-term funding for sustainable tourism projects and may be a good fit for investors who are interested in both financial returns and social impact. In Georgia, there are several impact investments funds such as Caucasus Nature Fund, which invest in sustainable tourism projects that conserve natural and cultural heritage. The Caucasus Nature Fund will allocate €870,000 for the development of such kind of national parks in Georgia as are: Borjom-Kharagauli, Mtirala and Pshav-Khevsureti between 2019 and 2021 (CNF. 2019). In 2021 CNF secured a grant from the Wyss Foundation for up to \$ 11 million in support for five new Protected Areas to be created in Georgia. CNF In 2022 will support to open two new Protected Areas in Georgia – in Racha and Shida-Kartli – to be legally established by the end of 2022 (CNF. 2021). From the point of view of improving the use of digital technologies for the tourism potential of Georgia and its development, two CENN projects are very important: "Digital Caucasus" and "Development of the Social Enterprise Ecosystem for Green Growth (SEED)", which consider employment of people. in the sector and the promotion of existing entrepreneurs.(CENN.2020)

2. **Green bonds:** Green bonds are debt securities issued to finance projects that have a positive environmental impact. They can be used to finance sustainable tourism projects, such as the construction of eco-friendly hotels, conservation projects, or renewable energy infrastructure. Green bonds have gained popularity in recent years and can provide an attractive source of funding for sustainable tourism projects in Georgia. So, Green Bonds: Green bonds are fixed-income financial instruments used to finance projects that have positive environmental or climate benefits. In 2019, the Georgian Energy Development Fund issued the country's first green bond to finance sustainable tourism projects (IMF,2022). IFC anchored the coun-

try's first \$20 million green bond under \$80 million issuance. To date, this is the largest placement of domestic corporate bonds in Georgia. In addition, the Asian Development Bank (ADB) has invested \$4 million in green bonds (NBG. 2023).

3. **Microfinance:** Microfinance institutions provide small loans to entrepreneurs and small businesses, including those in the tourism industry. In Georgia, microfinance institutions such as Crystal Fund and FINCA Georgia provide loans to tourism-related businesses to support sustainable tourism development (The World bank. 2019).

4. **Alternative Lending:** Fintech companies have introduced alternative lending models, such as peer-to-peer lending, which can connect borrowers in the tourism sector with individual lenders or investors. This provides an alternative source of financing for tourism businesses, particularly SMEs, that may face challenges accessing traditional bank loans.

5. **TBC Bank:** TBC Bank, one of the leading banks in Georgia, has a strong focus on fintech and has been working closely with businesses in the tourism sector. They provide various financial services and solutions tailored to the needs of tourism companies, including payment processing, lending, and digital banking services. TBC Company created "Space" the first fully digital bank both in Georgia and in the region . Space is a technologically sophisticated and large-scale next-generation digital bank that is on par with fintech companies firmly established in the international arena.

Implementing fintech in financing tourism in Georgia can bring several benefits to the industry and the overall sustainable development of the region. Here are some key benefits: Increased access to financing: Fintech solutions can provide greater access to financing for tourism businesses, entrepreneurs, and local communities. By leveraging digital platforms and alternative lending models, fintech can connect potential investors with tourism projects, overcoming traditional barriers to entry and increasing the availability of funds for sustainable tourism initiatives; Diversification of funding sources: Fintech services can diversify the sources of funding for sustainable tourism in Georgia. Crowdfunding platforms, peer-to-peer lending, and other fintech innovations can attract a broader range of investors, including individual backers and impact investors interested in supporting sustainable tourism. This reduces reliance on traditional banking institutions and broadens the funding landscape (Tsutskiridze, Charaia, 2023); Enhanced efficiency and transparency: Fintech enables streamlined financial processes and transparent transactions.

Conclusion and recommendation

In conclusion, financing sustainable tourism development in Georgia is not only an investment in the country's economic growth but also a commitment to preserving its unique natural and cultural heritage. By channeling financial resources towards sustainable initiatives, Georgia can attract responsible travelers, protect its environment, and foster the socio-economic well-being of local communities.

Sustainable tourism development in Georgia requires a collaborative effort from public and private sectors, as well as local communities. By leveraging innovative financing mechanisms and partnerships, such as public-private partnerships and impact investments, Georgia can unlock the potential for sustainable growth in its tourism sector while preserving its pristine landscapes and cultural traditions.

To attract financing for sustainable tourism in Georgia, it is crucial to emphasize the country's rich biodiversity, stunning landscapes, and diverse cultural heritage. By highlighting the value proposition and unique selling points of sustainable tourism in Georgia, such as eco-adventure tourism, agrotourism, and cultural experiences, investors can be incentivized to support projects that align with sustainable development goals.

Financial institutions and development banks can play a significant role in providing access to capital for sustainable tourism projects in Georgia. By integrating environmental and social risk assessments into their investment decisions, these institutions can support the development of environmentally friendly and socially responsible tourism initiatives.

The Georgian government has a pivotal role to play in facilitating the financing of sustainable tourism. By creating favorable policy frameworks, providing incentives, and supporting capacity-building initiatives, the government can attract both domestic and international investments to drive sustainable tourism development in the country.

Lastly, fostering awareness and education, as well as supporting professional orientation (Kvirkvaia et al., 2018) about the benefits of sustainable tourism among stakeholders, including local communities, tourism operators, and tourists, is essential. By promoting responsible travel practices and sustainable tourism principles, Georgia can create a positive cycle of engagement and support for sustainable tourism initiatives.

These conclusions highlight the importance of financing sustainable tourism development in Georgia, the need for collaboration and innovation, and the role of different stakeholders, including the government and financial institutions, in achieving sustainable outcomes.

Based on the research done we would like to provide several recommendations which could improve the financing process for sustainable tourism development in Georgia:

1. Engage international development organizations and donors: Seek partnerships with international development organizations, multilateral agencies, and donors that prioritize sustainable tourism development. Collaborate with them to secure financial support, technical assistance, and capacity-building programs.

2. Encourage private sector investment: Foster private sector investment in sustainable tourism by offering incentives such as tax breaks, subsidies, or preferential access to funding. Create an attractive investment environment that promotes sustainable tourism initiatives and demonstrates potential returns on investment.

3. Develop public-private partnerships: Foster collaboration between the public and private sectors to leverage resources, expertise, and funding. Encourage joint ventures and public-private partnerships to finance sustainable tourism projects. This can include infrastructure development, eco-lodges, and community-based tourism enterprises.

4. Explore crowdfunding and crowdsourcing platforms: Utilize crowdfunding and crowdsourcing platforms to raise funds for specific sustainable tourism projects. This approach allows individuals and organizations passionate about sustainable tourism to contribute financially and support initiatives directly.

5. Promote impact investment: Encourage impact investors who prioritize both financial returns and positive social and environmental impacts to invest in sustainable tourism projects. Highlight the potential benefits of sustainable tourism, such as job creation, community development, and conservation efforts.

6. Enhance financial literacy and capacity: Provide training and capacity-building programs for tourism stakeholders, including local communities, entrepreneurs, and project managers, to improve their financial literacy. This will empower them to develop strong business plans, attract investors, and effectively manage financial resources.

7. Develop innovative financing models: Explore innovative financing models such as green bonds, social impact bonds, or revenue-sharing agreements to fund sustainable tourism projects. These models can attract investors interested in aligning their financial goals with sustainable development objectives.

8. Establish monitoring and reporting mechanisms: Develop systems to monitor the utilization of funds allocated to sustainable tourism projects and report on their impact. Regularly evaluate the effectiveness of the financing process and make necessary adjustments to improve efficiency and maximize results.

By implementing these recommendations, Georgia can enhance the financing process for sustainable tourism development, attract investments, and ensure the long-term viability of sustainable initiatives in the Caucasian region.

References

1. A Tourism Strategy for Georgia – New Path Ahead (2015). Georgia National Tourism Strategy 2025, Volume 1: Situation Analysis Ministry of Infrastructure and Regional Development of Georgia (2019): Strategy for the Development of Georgia's Mountain Settlements in order to ensure equal and sustainable development of Georgian regions (2019-2023).
2. Abashidze, I. (2023). Permission Marketing Strategy Shaping Consumer Behaviour Through Online Communication Channels. *Baltic Journal of Economic Studies*, 9(2), 8-18.
3. Caucasus Nature Fund 2019 Annual Report. (2020). https://www.caucasus-nature-fund.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/CNF_annual_report_2020.pdf

4. Caucasus Nature Fund 2021 Annual Report. (2022), https://www.caucasus-nature-fund.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/CNF_annual_report_2021.pdf
5. Charaia, V., & Lashkhi, M. (2020). Georgia-China Economic Cooperation before and during Covid-19 Pandemic. *ECONOMICS*, (4), 43-53.
6. Charaia, V., Chochia, A., & Lashkhi, M. (2021). Promoting fintech financing for SME in S. Caucasian and baltic states, during the COVID-19 global pandemic. *Business, Management and Economics Engineering*, 19(2), 358-372.
7. Charaia, V., Lashkhi, M., & Lashkhi, M. (2022). Foreign direct investments during the economic crisis and armed conflict in the neighbourhood, Case of Georgia. *Globalization & Business*, 13, 51-56.
8. Digital Caucasus – Synergies and Digital Transformation of SMEs for Smart Economic Growth in the Caucasus Tourism Sector (2022). <http://www.cenn.org/digital-caucasus-synergies-and-digital-transformation-of-smes-for-smart-economic-growth-in-the-caucasus-tourism-sector/>
9. Dilanchiev, A., & Taktakishvili, T. (2021). Currency depreciation Nexus country's export: Evidence from Georgia. *Universal Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 9(5), 1116-1124.
10. Dredge, D., & Jenkins, J. (2011). Financing Sustainable Tourism Development: A Review of Concepts, Research, and Challenges. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 19(2), 239-254. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669582.2010.543896>
11. Ernazarov, A. (2019). Tourism development in Georgia. P. 44.
12. Georgia a country that remains attractive for IFIS in 2019 (2019). The World Bank. <https://www.ccifg.ge/news/n/news/georgia-a-country-that-remains-attractive-for-ifis-in-2019.html>
13. Georgia Beyond Arrivals. (2020). Emerging opportunities for Georgian firms in tourism value chains. <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/264181575569238865/pdf/Georgia-Beyond-Arrivals-Emerging-Opportunities-for-Georgian-Firms-in-Tourism-Value-Chains.pdf>
14. Georgian Tourism in Figures. (2016). Available at: gnta.ge/wp-content/uploads/2016/08/ENG.pdf; Georgian Tourism in Figures (2017), <https://gnta.ge/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/2017-ENG.pdf> GNTA.; Georgian Tourism in Figures (2018). <https://gnta.ge/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/2018-ENG.pdf>; Georgian Tourism in Figures (2019) https://gnta.ge/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/2019_ENG_PRINT.pdf.
15. Geostat (2022). Inbound tourism statistics Georgia. <https://www.geostat.ge/media/51279/Inbound-Tourism-Statistics----2022.pdf>
16. Geostat. (2022). Inbound Tourism. <https://www.geostat.ge/en/modules/categories/102/inbound-tourism>
17. Hall, C. M., & Jenkins, J. M. (2015). Financing Sustainable Tourism: A Model for Small Island Developing States. *Sustainability*, 7(5), 4906-4923. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su7054906>
18. IFC. (2022). ADB Invest in Georgia's First Green Bond to Boost Climate Finance. <https://georgiatoday.ge/ifc-adb-invest-in-georgias-first-green-bond-to-boost-climate-finance/>
19. Inbound Tourism Statistics - II Quarter, 2022-year <https://www.geostat.ge/en/single-news/2598/inbound-tourism-statistics-ii-quarter-2022-year>.
20. Kadagidze L., Piranashvili M. (2021). The Post-Pandemic World Tourism Revival Efforts - European Science Review (N5-6), Premier Publishing, Vienna, May-June. Pp. 79-83. <https://doi.org/10.29013/ESR-21-5.6-79-82>
21. Kadagidze L., Piranashvili M. (2018). Challenges of Tourism Business on the Example of Georgia's Capital – 11th International Conference for Cultural Tourism in Europe - Cultural Heritage as an Asset for Responsible and Sustainable Tourism – European Cultural Tourism Network in the frame of European Year Cultural Heritage; October 25-27. Pafos, Cyprus. http://www.culturaltourismnetwork.eu/uploads/5/0/6/0/50604825/ectn_conference_2018_programme_v9.pdf https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343676271_Challenges_of_Tourism_Business_on_the_Example_of_Georgia's_Capital
22. Kvirkvaia, M., Kikutadze, V., Sikharulidze, D., Shaburishvili, S., & Charaia, V. (2018). Study of factors affecting young people. *Globalization & Business*.
23. Lashkhi, M., Charaia, V., Boyarchuk, A., & Ebralidze, L. (2022). The Impact of Fintech on Financial Institutions: The Case of Georgia. *TalTech Journal of European Studies*, 12(2), 20-42.
24. Lashkhi, M., Ogbaidze, S., Lashkhi, M., & Charaia, V. (2022). Startup Access to Finance in Georgia and International Experience. *Ekonomisti*, <https://ekonomisti.tsu.ge/uploads/images/ek20222.pdf#page=49>
25. Meladze M., Koblianidze T., Piranashvili M. & Alaverdashvili S. (2022). Post-pandemic Employment Opportunities in Georgia's Hospitality Industry. *ESI Preprints*. <https://doi.org/10.19044/esipreprint.9.2022.p417>
26. Ministry of Economy and Sustainable Development & GNTA. (2015) Georgia National Tourism Strategy 2025, Volume 1: Situation Analysis Ministry of Infrastructure and Regional Development of Georgia (2019): Strategy for the Development of Georgia's Mountain Settlements in order to ensure equal and sustainable development of Georgian regions (2019-2023)
27. Ministry of Economy and Sustainable Development & GNTA. (2015) Georgia National Tourism Strategy 2025, Volume 1: Situation Analysis Ministry of Infrastructure and Regional Development of Georgia (2019): Strategy for the Development of Georgia's Mountain Settlements in order to ensure equal and sustainable development of Georgian regions (2019-2023)
28. Papava, V., & Charaia, V. (2020). The Economic Crisis and Some Challenges for the Georgian Economy. *GFSIS, Expert Opinion*, (136). https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3572124
29. Saarinen, J., & Rogerson, C. M. (2013). Financing Sustainable Tourism Development in Least

Developed Countries: Challenges and Opportunities. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 16(4), 321-328. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13683500.2013.832188>

30. Support Tourism in Georgia (2022). <https://www.indiegogo.com/projects/support-tourism-in-georgia#/>

31. SUSTAINABLE FINANCE TAXONOMY (2023).

<https://nbg.gov.ge/en/page/sustainable-finance-taxonomy>

32. The Government of Georgia and the World Bank Discuss the National Tourism Development Strategy 2025 (2014).

<https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/press-release/2014/12/03/the-government-of-georgia-and-the-world-bank-discuss-the-national-tourism-development-strategy-2025>

33. The Peace Project (2022). A Documentary About Bringing Liberal Judaism to Tbilisi, Georgia.

https://www.kickstarter.com/projects/tbilisi/the-peace-project?ref=discovery_location.

34. Tsutskiridze, G., & Charaia, V. (2023). The Impact of Non-Interest Income on the net Non-Interest Margin in the Conditions of Sharp Currency Fluctuations and the Trend of Gel Devaluation. *Deutsche Internationale Zeitschrift für Zeitgenössische Wissenschaft*, (56).

35. UNWTO. (2015). Financing Sustainable Tourism Development: A Global Perspective. UNWTO. Retrieved from <https://www.e-unwto.org/doi/book/10.18111/9789284417307>

36. WTTC (2021). Research reveals global Travel & Tourism sector suffered a loss of almost US\$4.5 trillion in 2020 due to the impact of COVID-19. <https://wttc.org/news-article/global-tandt-sector-suffered-a-loss-of-almost-us4-trillion-in-2020>

DEVELOPMENT OF ANTIMONOPOLY POLICY IN GEORGIA

Slava Fetelava

Doctor of Economics (PhD), Associate Professor
School of Business and Management
Grigol Robakidze University, Georgia

Tamar Gamsakhurdia

Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor,
School of Business and Management
Grigol Robakidze University, Georgia

Abstract

The development of an Antimonopoly Policy is important for the economic development of Georgia, as it helps to foster competition, protect consumer rights, and ensure fair business practices. Here are a few key reasons why the development of an Antimonopoly Policy is significant: promoting competition, protecting consumer rights, ensuring market efficiency, attracting investment and enhancing business environment. In conclusion, the development of an Antimonopoly Policy in Georgia is crucial for promoting competition, protecting consumer rights, ensuring market efficiency, attracting investment, and aligning with international standards. It provides a framework for fair business practices, stimulates economic development, and contributes to a healthy and competitive business environment.

In the process of the research are used general scientific methods (systemic, structural, functional) and private methods (graphic and those of conformity). Official statistical data existing in the country as well as the data and evaluations officially published by international organizations are also used.

Keywords: Competition law, Competition policy, Antitrust, Consumer protection, Economic regulation

Introduction

In Georgia, as well as in most post-socialist countries, the period of transition to a market economy was characterized by great difficulties and resistance. Obviously, the process of modifying the country's economy on the rails of the market economy was not simple and easy to implement, bringing new, unfaced challenges (Anguridze et al., 2015; Papava, Charaia, 2021). Security problems and modern challenges of the Georgian national currency. Tbilisi State University.). However, it is also clear that in all those countries where this process started and did not achieve any significant success, the main reason for this success was the political will of each individual state, one of the most important elements of which is the realization of a consistent anti-monopoly policy, which in turn must be harmonized. with the outside world and should not

contradict the norms and international obligations established by international standards, at the same time considering major global and local events, supporting or destabilizing implementation of new approaches, for instance Covid-19 global pandemic (Charaia et al., 2021) and/or modern financial instruments bringing new reality to the market (Lashkhi et al., 2022).

Georgia, as a market-oriented country, from the very first year of gaining independence, set a goal to promote free trade and competition, providing equal opportunities for the business and professional (Kvirkaia et al., 2018), to serve the system. The achievement of which would be impossible without the presence of effective levers to identify and prevent the elements hindering the market economy. The latter was achievable precisely under the conditions of